

THE IMPORTANCE OF CULTURAL AWARENESS IN TOURISM IN THE SAMPLE OF ENGLISH PHRASES AND IDIOMS

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Abstract. *Cultural awareness in tourism plays a vital role in fostering respectful interactions between travellers and local communities. This article explores key English phrases and idioms encapsulating the significance of understanding and appreciating diverse cultures while travelling.*

Keywords: *cultural awareness, respect, customs, adaptation, understanding, diversity, kindness, connections, experiences, opportunities, positivity, global community.*

Аннотация. *Культурная осведомленность в туризме играет жизненно важную роль в развитии уважительного взаимодействия между путешественниками и местными сообществами. В этой статье рассматриваются ключевые английские фразы и идиомы, которые отражают важность понимания и признания различных культур во время путешествий.*

Ключевые слова: *культурная осведомленность, уважение, обычаи, адаптация, понимание, разнообразие, доброта, связи, опыт, возможности, позитивность, глобальное сообщество.*

Анотасија. *Turizmda madaniy xabardorlik sayohatchilar va mahalliy hamjamiyatlar o'rtasida o'zaro hurmatli munosabatlarni rivojlantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu maqola sayohat paytida turli madaniyatlarni tushunish va qadrlashning ahamiyatini aks ettiruvchi asosiy inglizcha iboralar va idiomalarni o'rganadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *madaniy xabardorlik, hurmat, urf-odatlar, moslashish, tushunish, xilma-xillik, mehribonlik, aloqalar, tajribalar, imkoniyatlar, ijobiylik, global hamjamiyat.*

When in Rome, do as the Romans do.

English proverb

Cultural awareness is the understanding and appreciation of the differences and similarities between cultures. Collins COBUILD Advanced Learner's Dictionary defines it: "Someone's **cultural awareness** is their **understanding** of the **differences** between themselves and people from other **countries** or other **backgrounds**, **especially** differences in **attitudes** and **values**". It involves recognizing and respecting cultural differences, acknowledging how they impact communication and interactions, and adapting behaviours accordingly. This awareness helps in fostering positive relationships and avoiding misunderstandings in diverse environments. It can also enhance personal growth by broadening one's perspectives and reducing biases.

In today's interconnected world, people from different cultures, backgrounds, and countries are constantly on the move, exploring new destinations, and experiencing diverse cultures. As a result, cultural awareness has emerged as a vital aspect of success in the hospitality and tourism industry. Cultural awareness is becoming increasingly important in the field of tourism as travellers seek authentic experiences when visiting new places. Cross-cultural awareness is a process or desire to adapt to another country or culture that is different from its

own. Understanding local customs, traditions, and expressions can enhance tourists' appreciation of their destination and foster positive cross-cultural encounters. Cultural differences have a significant impact on communication methods and relationships. Furthermore, cross-cultural awareness not only gives people an incentive to understand their own culture but also can develop attitudes that recognize and accommodate cultural differences. Therefore, cross-cultural awareness is regarded as a driving force to develop skills and abilities to overcome cultural disparities. Cross-cultural awareness may also include the desire to know about other countries or other cultures through tourism activity. Along with the increase of cross-cultural tourism, the consumers' tastes changed from repetitive and passive activities to pursuing new experiences.

Travelers should respect and learn about the culture and people of the place they visit. This includes trying local foods, wearing appropriate clothing, and being mindful of social norms. Recognizing and appreciating differences among individuals and communities enriches our own lives. Being aware of diverse perspectives and learning from others allows us to broaden our horizons and build stronger relationships with people around the world.

Discovering shared interests and values can create powerful bonds between individuals and groups, even across vast cultural divides. Engaging in open dialogue and finding opportunities for collaboration promotes empathy, understanding, and lasting connections. In conclusion, cultural awareness is essential for enriching travel experiences and fostering positive relationships between tourists and host communities. By embracing these phrases and their meanings, travellers can contribute to a more respectful and harmonious global community, ensuring that their journeys are not only enjoyable but also culturally sensitive.

Learning about culture opens a window to understanding the 'why' behind the language. Have you ever wondered why certain phrases exist or why English speakers say things a certain way?

The cultural background gives insight into these riddles. For example, understanding the importance of tea in British culture can transform a simple sentence like "Let's grab a cuppa" (let's have a cup of tea together) into a friendly invitation to converse and make connections. Understanding cultural differences reduces obstacles and builds bridges. Knowing about customs, humour, and politeness allows you to speak English and communicate successfully by sharing your thoughts and emotions.

Traditionally, British good manners insist on politeness, at all times. This means saying please and thank you, forming an organized queue when waiting for a bus (even if you are the only person at the bus stop!), and saying excuse me if someone is blocking your way.

In Russian culture, for example, the British style of, “Could you possibly open the window, please?” can seem over-the-top and unnecessary. Equally, “open the window”, might sound impolite to the British ear, as we are used to indirect questions to show politeness. It doesn't mean that in Russian please and thank you are not required, these sentiments can often be demonstrated in other ways, such as through respectful gestures or polite forms of address. Please and thank you are less common in informal contexts, especially with friends or family, due to the group's expected familiarity and intimacy.

People rarely talk using literal language exclusively, most of all they use idiomatic phrases that communicate nonliteral meaning like “let sleeping dogs lie” with its translation into Uzbek as “yoriqlik qozon, yoriqligicha qolsin, in Russian it sounds like “Спящего пса не буди; “a storm in a teacup” sounds into Uzbek as “pashadan fil yasash”; in Russian – “много шума из ничего”

or “it rains cats and dogs” which in Uzbek is translated as “yomg’ir paqirlab yog’moqda”, in Russian it is translated as “дождь льет как из ведра”.

We are not able to translate idioms from one language to another in a direct way, we should take into account their meaning, what they mean in this culture, and what symbols they convey with these words in their culture.

By embracing these concepts, tourists can promote cultural sensitivity, enhance their own experiences and contribute positively to the communities they visit. As English people say "The world is your oyster" which means culturally aware travellers can fully enjoy and appreciate the diverse experiences available globally. Understanding the cultural nuances, traditions, and social norms of a destination enhances the travel experience, minimizes misunderstandings, and promotes positive cross-cultural exchanges. This awareness is particularly important when navigating the use of language, including English phrases and idioms, which can often carry different connotations or meanings in various cultural contexts. By recognizing and adapting to these linguistic subtleties, tourists can demonstrate respect and sensitivity, ultimately enriching their own travel experiences and contributing to more harmonious global interactions, experiences, and contributing positively to the communities they visit. Being culturally aware is an important part of staying safe and informed when travelling abroad. By being respectful, avoiding stereotypes, learning about the culture, being aware of nonverbal communication, and being open-minded, you can ensure a positive and rewarding travel experience. In today's interconnected world, it is more important than ever to expand our cultural awareness and appreciation. As we navigate through life, it is easy to develop tunnel vision, focusing solely on our own experiences and perspectives. However, by broadening our horizons and embracing the diversity of cultures around us, we can gain a deeper understanding of the world and foster greater empathy and respect for others by embracing travel, language learning, cultural exchange programs, reading and research, attending cultural events, and leveraging online platforms, we can continuously expand our horizons, challenge our perspectives, and develop a greater appreciation for the diverse world we live in.

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